

SAMANDAR VOHIDOV'S LITERARY MASTERY IN TAXMIS
MUXAMMAS

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Abstract: The article highlights several key aspects of Samandar Vohidov's literary mastery in composing *taxmis muxammas*. Demonstrating a deep understanding of classical poetic traditions, he skillfully connects his own lines to Alisher Navoiy's ghazals of various themes—*hamd* (praise), *ashiqona* (romantic), and *orifona* (mystical, philosophical). In transforming the couplets into five-line stanzas, Vohidov meticulously preserves the poem's original meter, rhyme, and refrain, which is a clear indication of his refined poetic craftsmanship.

Key words: The science of aruz, the science of rhyme, ramali musammani maksur, dedication, ghazal, qasida, mukhammas, masnavi, classical poetics. Creating *taxmis muxammas* is considered the second type of *muxammas* creation. R. Orzibekov refers to such *muxammas* as *tazmin muxammas*. This terminology is justified, as "tazmin" means "basis" or "foundation," indicating that in creating such *muxammas*, another poet's or author's ghazal serves as the foundational text. *Muxammas* created by the *tazmin* method are also called the art of adding five lines to each couplet of a ghazal. This also implies the existence of a basis. To create the five-line additions to ghazal couplets, the poet selects a ghazal written by himself or by a poet from the past or contemporary, preserving its meter, rhyme, and refrain, and adds three lines before each couplet according to certain poetic principles. By doing so, the poet somewhat expands the theme of the original ghazal and demonstrates his artistic skill while maintaining the poetic elements of meter, rhyme, and refrain. This, of course, demands great artistic mastery from the poet. Indeed, when a poet links his *taxmis muxammas* to a classical poet's ghazal, he must take into account the original poet's ideological views, mastery of word usage, and several other factors. Samandar Vohidov, having deeply studied these poetic requirements for creating *taxmis muxammas*, is considered a talented poet with 58 such works to his name. The fact that 50 of his *taxmis muxammas* are linked to the ghazals of Alisher Navoi alone attests to the poet's high talent. The great poet Navoi, as an incomparable talent, skillfully employs mystical terms, expressions, concepts, allegories, and symbols in his ghazal couplets to create artistic discoveries and

interpret his divine-spiritual views. Matching his skill in adding lines requires similar talent from the creator of the taxmis muxammas. Samandar Vohidov has also linked taxmis muxammas to the ghazals of other great poets such as Husayniy and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, as well as to the ghazals of the contemporary poet Jamol Kamol, who masterfully translated unique masterpieces of Eastern classical literature like Jalaluddin Rumi's *Masnavi-ye Ma'navi*. Furthermore, he has created taxmis muxammas on the ghazals of Persian-Tajik poets like Imlobukhori and Hayrat. In these cases, he translated the Persian-Tajik ghazals into Uzbek, using the form "ghazal translated with a ghazal." To highlight the poet's mastery in this regard, we consider his taxmis muxammas linked to the ghazals of Navoi, Husayniy, Hayrat, and Jamol Kamol. When adding taxmis muxammas to Alisher Navoi's ghazals, Samandar Vohidov pays attention to their thematic diversity. He has composed taxmis muxammas on ghazals ranging from the praise poem beginning with "Ashraqt min aksi shamsil – ka'si anvoril - hudo" to a hasbi-hal ghazal starting with "Men jahondin kechdim-u, kechmas mening jonimdan el," as well as on love-mystical and friendship-themed ghazals like "Har labing o'lganni tirgizmakka jono, jon erur, Bu jihatdin bir-bisi birla jonajon erur." All these demonstrate Samandar Vohidov's deep admiration and thorough study of the magic and mysteries characteristic of Navoi's ghazals.

We attempt to clarify this with an analysis of his taxmis muxammas linked to a 9-couplet ghazal beginning with the line "Ashraqt min aksi shamsil – ka'si anvoril - hudo," which is complex and adorned with mystical terminology. The first stanza of this taxmis is composed of the following lines:

Bu yurak mulkini qay kun ayladı ishq istilo,
Keng jahon menga jahonmas, bo'ldi dashti Karbalo,
Hajr o'ti komida tilg'a kelganida "alvido",
Ashraqt min aksi shamsil – ka'si anvoril – hudo
"Yor aksin mayda ko'r" deb jomdin chiqdi sado [Saylanma IV, 180].

When Samandar Vohidov composed a *muxammas* based on Alisher Navoi's famous *hamd* (praise) ghazal, as seen in the opening stanza he incorporated, he preserved the original ghazal's meter and rhyme. To broaden the meaning expressed in the ghazal's opening couplet, he begins his first line by interpreting it as the moment love invaded the realm of the heart—portraying the heart as a kingdom overtaken by love. From that day onward, he artistically conveys that this vast world has no longer appeared to him as a world, but as the desert of Karbala. As is well known, the desert of Karbala is the site where the Prophet

Muhammad's (peace be upon him) beloved grandson Husayn, along with his sons, nephews, and companions, were martyred after suffering hunger and thirst in a brutal battle against their enemies. In the Islamic world, this event is seen as one of the greatest tragedies. The poet's skill lies in drawing a poetic parallel between the transformation of his heart—since it became a dwelling place for love—and the desert of Karbala, using a *talmeh* (allusion) to convey the sorrow and suffering associated with it. When the word “farewell” reaches the lips of the lyrical hero, who is tormented by the fires of separation, that is, when the moment of death arrives, the line “Ashraqat min aksi shamsil – ka’si anvoril – hudo” (“The reflection of God’s radiant sun shone from the goblet”) is heard as a sudden cry from the goblet, saying “Behold the reflection of the Beloved in the wine.” In linking his third line of the opening stanza to Navoi’s bayt, Vohidov deliberately leaves it as an unfinished phrase, artistically merging it into Navoi’s poetic flow. From the third to fifth lines of the stanza, the meaning becomes clear: “When, in the midst of the fire of separation, the word ‘farewell’ was uttered (coincidentally), just like the light of guidance shining from the goblet reflecting the sun, a voice cried out from the goblet: ‘Behold the Beloved’s reflection in the wine.’” Here, the **goblet** is a symbolic expression of the lyrical hero’s heart, filled to the brim with divine love, inviting one to see the Beloved—i.e., God—reflected in the wine of the heart overflowing with love. It becomes evident that Samandar Vohidov artistically conveys that through enduring the torments on the path of love, the true seeker comes to witness the manifestation (*tajalli*) of God in their heart. In addition to maintaining rhyme consistency, the poet also employs the metaphor “kingdom of the heart” in the first line, which lexically and semantically binds his own verses to Navoi’s *matla*. In the following couplet of the great poet’s ghazal, mystic concepts and terminology such as **saqi** (cupbearer) and **the wine of unity** (*wahdat mayi*) are used. Samandar Vohidov, in turn, succeeds in composing lines that correspond meaningfully and thematically with those mystical ideas. Samandar Vohidov, in his *muxammas* compositions linked to the ghazals of classical poets and Jamol Kamol, proves himself to be a masterful artist in expressing personal reflection (*hasbi hol*), fate, and the contrast between dreams and the often incompatible destiny of love. He elevates the use of symbolic imagery to the level of artistic discovery, skillfully conveying philosophical and spiritual insights about life through unique and richly crafted metaphors. His *muxammas* verses also show his talent for expressing emphasis and deeper meaning with poetic precision. Vohidov demonstrates remarkable skill in creating symbolic images and representations

in certain ghazals. The poetic thought or literary scene introduced in the opening couplet (*matla*) is carefully developed around a central symbolic image, and this idea or scene is gradually expanded through the progression of the stanzas. The lyrical persona in such ghazals often takes on the character of an *arif*—a spiritually enlightened figure—which adds further depth and importance to the work. The portrayal of this spiritually mature character suggests that the poet possesses not only great creative talent but also profound life experience and a deep, insightful view of existence and society. Through symbolic imagery, Vohidov successfully conveys these qualities in his ghazals, confirming his stature as a highly gifted and thoughtful poet.

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